

The Real, Imaginary, and Symbolic Orders: Lacanian Analysis of the Film *Enemy*

Psychoanalysis is one of the most pivotal methods used to analyze the unconscious mind, concentrating on the hidden aspects of human characteristics. This approach has been widely integrated into various art forms, including literature, theater, and cinema, to examine the deeper layers of meanings. Jacques Lacan is one of the most prominent figures in psychoanalysis. Lacan was a French psychoanalyst who lived in the 20th century and provided important contributions to psychoanalysis. The fundamental structure of Lacan's psychoanalysis consists of Register Theory, namely Real, Imaginary, and Symbolic Orders (Registers). Imaginary Order is the realm that orients our experience through fantasy and ego formation (Johnston, Evans). According to Lacan, this order emerges in the Mirror Stage, where a child, for the first time, recognizes their reflection as an idealized self, forming the foundation of ego (2). The image in the mirror is associated with an illusory view of self and reflects how society perceives us. The second term, Symbolic Order, refers to the realm of language, societal norms, and structures that monitor human relationships and identity. As Ross states, "Whereas imaginary identification posits some ground of shared essence, symbolic identification involves the subject's identification with a prohibition, with that which is not allowed (because impossible), and thus with absence or lack as the truth of subjectivity" (10). The Real Order, the third term of Lacanian Psychoanalysis, is often a challenging concept to define and brings about confusion regarding its meaning. This order basically refers to the realm where the language does not exist and, therefore, is impossible to visualize or articulate. It is often linked to raw, unmediated reality that cannot be fully articulated and encompasses the indescribable, chaotic aspects of existence, such as primal needs and traumas. The film *Enemy*, directed by Denis Villeneuve in 2013, is an adaptation of José Saramago's novel *The Double*. The story focuses on a history teacher, Adam Bell, whose

monotonous life is disrupted when he notices an actor in a movie who looks strikingly identical to him. Driven by curiosity, he arranges a meeting with the actor in a hotel room, only to realize that they are identical, which leads to a series of escalating events. Denis Villeneuve's *Enemy* can be read through the lens of Lacanian analysis as it not only has a psychological depth but also contains a handful of metaphors and symbols contributing to its complex narrative. In this paper, Lacan's Imaginary, Symbolic, and Real Orders will be used to analyze the protagonist's psychodynamics. In *Enemy*, when Lacan's Imaginary, Symbolic, and Real Orders are applied, it can be claimed that the protagonist undergoes psychological fragmentation.

There have been a few articles regarding the analysis of the film *Enemy*. One of the prominent studies on the film is *Film and Psychoanalysis: A Freudian Psychoanalytic Reading of Denis Villeneuve's Enemy* by Swarup Das. In this article, Das primarily focuses on how the film *Enemy* can be analyzed through the lens of Freud's Psychodynamics, namely id, ego, and superego. He assigns the characters in the film to the id, ego, and superego. In this way, he analyzes the characters' psyche and proposes a thorough understanding of the film's meaning. While he mainly focuses on Freudian psychoanalysis, one of his conclusions is that women are reflected as objects of desire in the film. Ultimately, the author concludes that women are passive, and relationships between them are not present in the film. That is, he also points out Feminism film theory. Another article that analyzes the film *Enemy* is *Beyond Complexity: Narrative Experimentation and Genre Development in Enemy* by Melanie Kreitler. Kreitler mainly discusses how the film's complex narrative is open to interpretation and in which ways the narrative of the film can be deciphered. She constantly draws analogies between several films that contain ambiguity and *Enemy*, and by doing so, she points out several interpretative paths in the movie. Extending these discussions, Leindecker proposes a different perspective analyzing the film *Enemy* in his article *Taking Split Personalities to the Next Level: Perturbatory Narration in Enemy*. The author concentrates on how the film rebuilds the

convention of narration regarding split personality. He makes a comparison between *Enemy* and the film *Fight Club* at first and then delves into analyzing the film in terms of its perturbatory narration. That is to say, he focuses on the structure of narration rather than delving into the psychologies of the characters (Das, Kreidler, Leindecker). In this paper, the primary concern will be about how the psyche of the protagonist can be analyzed through the lens of Lacan's Imaginary, Symbolic, and Real Orders. In this way, a unique perspective, Lacanian analysis, will be presented, analyzing how the protagonist's psychology is fragmented.

In *Enemy*, the protagonist's psychological state is affected by the Imaginary Order, particularly seen through his relationships with his mother and his double, both of which lead to a profound psychological fragmentation. In the film, the dependency of the protagonist on his mother and his initial encounter with his double points out his fragmented psyche, which occurs in Imaginary Order. This fragmentation can be initially observed in his dependency on his mother, a central figure in his psyche. In several scenes, his mother is depicted as a dominant figure, having a sense of control over his life. For instance, in the opening scene, the protagonist listens to a voice message from his mother, which denotes that his mother knows many small details and changes in his life (*Enemy*, 00:01:21-00:21:45). His mother's controlling and monotonous voice tone underscores how she is an important and dominant figure in the protagonist's life. Another scene also reveals this relationship: When the protagonist states, "I don't like blueberries," his mother dismissively responds, "Of course, you do, and they are good for you" (*Enemy*, 01:00:12-01:00:20). This scene may initially seem an ordinary scene to the audiences. Analyzing through the Lacanian lens, however, one may argue that this scene reveals how his mother knows his favorites and needs better than him. Taking into consideration that the protagonist is an adult and a reputable history professor, this scene, in fact, connotes a deeper meaning regarding his dependency on his mother, which is an important concept in Imaginary Order. Indeed, Ulmer points out the mother figure in Lacan's mirror stage, the central theme in

Imaginary Order, stating that “[One] idealization that derives from the mirror-phase is the identification with the image of the “Mother” who holds the child up before the mirror. The jubilation experienced in identifying with the “omnipotence” of this figure [...] gives rise to another idealization—the ideal ego” (69). That is to say, in the mirror stage occurring in Imaginary Order, the mother figure is of utmost importance since the individual’s identity is initially shaped through their connection with the mother. This relationship shapes their understanding of themselves and their needs, rooted in the mother’s perceived omnipotence. Referring back to the scenes, since the protagonist is still dependent on his mother, and his mother understands his desires and needs better than him (in the blueberry scene), one could argue that this leads to the creation of the *ideal ego*—a part of the protagonist that still views his mother as an omnipotent figure. This relationship underscores the dominant image of his mother in his psyche, revealing that his psyche is fragmented due to his mother’s pervasive influence that prevents him from fully demonstrating his individuality. This relationship, therefore, suggests that his sense of self is fractured between his role as an autonomous individual and his reliance on his mother’s omnipotent presence.

The Imaginary Order’s other impact on the protagonist’s identity crises can be seen through his initial interaction with his double. In the film, some scenes depict the protagonist’s initial encounter with his doppelgänger—the actor that he saw in a movie looking identical to him— and his mixed feelings about this discovery, which utterly resembles Lacan's concept of the mirror stage within the Imaginary Order. For example, in the scene where they meet in a hotel room for the first time, they find out that they are identical; even their scars are the same. In this scene, they are standing face to face, looking at their hands simultaneously, which resembles a person looking at his image through a mirror (*Enemy*, 00:50:40-00:51:45). This moment is an epitome of Lacan’s mirror stage, and therefore, can be analyzed in this sense. Examining their

initial encounter deeper, one can suggest that his double represents his “idealized” self, revealing his fragmented psyche. Indeed, elaborating on Lacan’s mirror stage, Ross argues that:

[In the mirror phase] dual recognition produces two results, both of which are aspects of the same reaction. The first of these is that the infant admires the wholeness of the specular image and desires identification with that image. This is the formation of the ideal ego, which may loosely be conceived of as the unarticulated thought, “I want to be that (in which I perceive an ideal version of myself)” (7).

This implies that the image appearing in the mirror offers a specular image, a projection of the ideal ego, which the individual both admires and desires to identify with. In the context of the film, considering the protagonist—a history teacher— and his double—a film star— the “idealization” becomes more apparent. Given that the protagonist’s life is monotonous and stuck in a routine, his doppelganger, as a specular image, holds up a mirror to the protagonist’s dissatisfaction with his current life. Just as the infant looks at his reflection, the protagonist finds in this specular image a sense of wholeness, and by doing so, he encounters the limits of identification. Here, then, it can be stated that the protagonist’s sense of self is fragmented since his one part of himself, his idealized self, remains tantalizingly out of reach. Therefore, it can be concluded that the protagonist’s interactions with his double highlight his internal struggle to integrate this idealized image into his current life, leading to a fragmented sense of self.

The protagonist’s internal conflicts are also rooted in the Symbolic Order, which can be seen through his roles as both husband and history professor. In the film, while the protagonist’s relationship with his pregnant wife and his mistress reveals his internal conflicts regarding societal constraints, his repeating history lectures about dictatorship and control metaphorically symbolize social norms and societal constraints that he faces in his life, both pointing to the Symbolic Order. The protagonist’s internal conflicts are initially reflected in his handicap monitoring his role as a husband. For example, in one scene, after the protagonist meets his double

in the hotel room, he secretly follows his double and encounters his double's girlfriend, Mary. When he encounters Mary, he becomes amazed by her, and even though he has a pregnant wife, Helen, he desires to sleep with Mary (*Enemy*, 00:55:00-00:59:00). Encountering Mary for the first time evokes a forbidden desire in the protagonist's psyche that contradicts his obligations as a husband and soon-to-be father. This moment exemplifies Lacan's idea of the Symbolic Order. As Strecher suggests, "According to Lacan, then, the Symbolic Order (though constituted by ourselves) always intervenes, steps between ourselves and the Other, the object of our desire. This process is always grounded in language, in the intervention via language of symbols between us and the object of our desire." (114). That is to say, Symbolic Order structures the way individuals pursue their desires through societal codes, mediated through language. From this perspective, for the protagonist, the societal expectations encoded in language—words like "husband," "father," and the vows he has taken—function as a powerful structure that governs his psyche. Indeed, one could argue that in the scene where the protagonist secretly follows his doppelganger's girlfriend, Mary, and feels an illicit desire toward her, he contradicts the societal structure that promotes fidelity and fatherhood within the Symbolic Order. Although the Symbolic Order intervenes between himself and "the Other"—in this case, this is his desire towards Mary—he fails to reconcile his desires with the societal codes. In a sense, he swims against the current of the Symbolic Order. On the other hand, he continues to show intimacy and care toward his wife, Helen, which suggests that one part of himself is still connected to his role as a husband. Yet this connection stands as a stark contrast to his forbidden desires toward Mary. At this point, it can be concluded that the protagonist's psyche is fragmented between his one side aligning with societal norms as a husband and his other side, who desires to be with another woman. Therefore, it can be concluded that the protagonist undergoes psychological fragmentation, stemming from Symbolic Order.

The protagonist's psychological fragmentation is further highlighted in his role as a history professor regarding the Symbolic Order. For instance, in every lecture, he states the same words over and over again, "Control... It's all about control. Every dictatorship has one obsession, and that's it. And it is important to remember this, that this is a pattern that repeats itself throughout history." (Enemy, 01:29:40-01:30:50). In these scenes, the only change is the sitting arrangements of the students in the class. Therefore, one could assume that this scene symbolizes his subconscious recognition of the societal structure and its repetitive nature, highlighting his own experience of being controlled by external forces, including his role as a history professor. This sense of repetition directly pertained to the Symbolic Order. As Evans further emphasizes, "The concept of repetition is linked with that of the complex—an internalized social structure which the subject repeatedly and compulsively re-enacts. [...] He [Lacan] increasingly uses the term 'insistence' to refer to the repetition compulsion" (167). That is to say, the repetition of language (the central theme of Symbolic Order) is not merely a habit but a compulsion associated with internalized social structures. Viewing the protagonist's history lectures from this lens, it can be claimed that the concept of the "insistence of speech" finds a compelling reflection in the protagonist's lectures where the act of teaching history becomes an almost "compulsive re-enactment" of social structures he is exposed by the Symbolic Order. His emphasis on control as a historical constant becomes, in itself, a profound reflection of the control imposed upon him by the Symbolic Order. And yet, this awareness does not allow him to break free of the societal structure; instead, it amplifies his fragmented psyche, forcing him to be restricted in a cycle of repetition he cannot transcend. It can be concluded, then, that the protagonist's role as a history teacher underscores his fragmented psyche, symbolizing his entrapment within the societal constructs imposed by Symbolic Order that he subconsciously resents yet is unable to escape.

The final scene, in which the protagonist's wife transforms into a giant spider, underscores how the Real Order fractures the protagonist's psyche. Toward the end of the film, the protagonist begins to reconcile with his wife, Helen, as their fractured relationship shows signs of repair. Yet, this fragile harmony is short-lived. The following morning, the protagonist, with a sense of relief that their issues seem resolved, stumbles upon the key to the underground club, where married men gather to break free of their commitment to their wives. Upon finding the key, his thoughts immediately shift, and he resolves to revisit the club. He calls out to his wife to inform her that he's stepping out (carefully omitting his hidden intention), but she doesn't respond. Consequently, he enters the room where Helen just went in, only to suddenly encounter that she has transformed into a giant tarantula. This sudden encounter evokes a feeling of shock in the protagonist's face (*Enemy*, 01:24:10-01:26:50). At this point, one can state that this unexpected event disrupts the protagonist's attempt to control his life, one of the central themes of Lacan's Real Order. Malcolm Bowie explains this notion of the Real through a series of examples, including "a tile falling on to the head of a passer-by" or "a knock on the door that interrupts a dream," which highlights how the Real disrupts the symbolic and imaginary constructs we live within (103). As Ross further comments, "[...] the 'tile falling on the head of a passer-by' is not a direct intervention of the real, but an event through which the real makes itself felt in its sheer contingency, its materiality, and its disruption of the order imposed on the raw material of the world by the symbolic acts of humans (4). That is to say, Lacan's Real Order occurs not through its direct presence but through the structural disruptions it causes. It is the contingency that surrounds individuals' lives, standing in stark contrast to Symbolic Order. Revisiting the final scene through this lens, one could state that the protagonist's belief in the key to the underground club as a means of escape is, in itself, an illusion. He perceives it as a path to freedom from his marital commitment, yet this illusion is disrupted moments later when he encounters his wife's transformation into a giant spider. Just as Lacan's analogy of "the tile falling on a passerby's

head”, this unforeseen and shocking event disrupts the protagonist’s attempt to establish control over his life, leaving him face-to-face with the contingency and unpredictability of the Real. Thus, Helen’s transformation into a spider is not merely a fantastical occurrence; rather, it serves as a reminder of his inner conflict. On one side, he is driven by a desire for fidelity, while on the other, he seeks to establish autonomy and control over his life. This sudden encounter with the spider highlights the impossibility of resolving this tension, as the Real disrupts his sense of self with its sheer contingency. Hence, the final scene underscores the protagonist’s psychological fragmentation as his dual impulses—toward fidelity and autonomy—are irreconcilable and disrupted by the Real.

In conclusion, the film *Enemy* offers a complex narrative and psychological elements through its intricate storyline. While several studies attempt to uncover the hidden meanings and themes of the film, this paper provides a distinctive contribution by applying Lacan’s psychoanalytic theory of the Real, Symbolic, and Imaginary Orders to analyze the protagonist’s fragmented psychology. The protagonist’s fragmented self is analyzed in terms of each of the three orders separately. By analyzing the film in terms of Imaginary Order, it turns out that his relationship with his mother and his doppelganger drives him into psychological fragmentation. From the view of Symbolic Order, it is concluded that the protagonist’s inability to reconcile Symbolic Order, as seen through his role as a husband and as a history teacher, further evolves into a fractured psyche. Lastly, an analysis of the film in terms of Real Order revealed how the spider motif in the final scene highlights his ongoing fragmented psychology. In this paper, Lacan’s theory provided a well-established framework to explore the protagonist’s psychodynamics, which offers valuable insights into the complexities of his psychological fragmentation. And yet, this analysis remains limited in scope by focusing solely on the protagonist and, by doing so, leaves the other characters’ psychology unexplored. Future studies could enrich the discussions by also focusing on the other characters. Moreover, as it has always

been said, the ones who make meaning are viewers. The same also goes for the *Enemy*. There is still open room for different interpretations, and analyzing the film from different perspectives will not only deepen the understanding of its complexities but also enrich studies by practically applying psychoanalytic theories, particularly in the context of film analysis.

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